

Integration of Support Vector Machine and Bayesian Neural Network for Data Mining and Classification

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Abstract—Several combinations of the preprocessing algorithms, feature selection techniques and classifiers can be applied to the data classification tasks. This study introduces a new accurate classifier, the proposed classifier consist from four components: Signal-to-Noise as a feature selection technique, support vector machine, Bayesian neural network and AdaBoost as an ensemble algorithm. To verify the effectiveness of the proposed classifier, seven well known classifiers are applied to four datasets. The experiments show that using the suggested classifier enhances the classification rates for all datasets.

Keywords—AdaBoost, Bayesian neural network, Signal-to-Noise, support vector machine, MCMC.

I. INTRODUCTION

CLASSIFICATION is one of the oldest and the most important method of data mining. Supervised classification means learning from data that is already classified correctly, and using the pre-built model to classify the new data. Four important criteria can be used to compare between the classifiers: the percent of instances that are classified correctly (the accuracy), the computational cost of both learning model and testing process (the speed), the ability to cope with noisy or missing data (the robustness) and the ability to cope with very large amounts of data (the scalability). Many classification methods are introduced in the previous studies, K-nearest neighbors (KNN) is one of the simplest and useful methods. The main idea of KNN is that it treats all the samples as points in the m-dimensional space and classifies the new data by a vote of K-nearest training instances as determined by some distance metric, typically Euclidean distance [1]. Multilayered Perceptrons (Artificial Neural Networks) have been used in data mining and classification. The standard ANN algorithm adjusts weights by propagating the error between network outputs and employs gradient descent optimization to minimize the error function. Several modified NN models are developed and implemented in the previous studies, see[2], [3]. Radial Basis Function (RBF) networks have been also widely applied in many science and engineering fields [4]. Each hidden unit in the RBF network implements a radial activation function and each output unit implements a weighted sum of hidden units outputs. To

complete the training process a set of linear equations must be solved. Naive Bayes classifiers are very simple Bayesian networks which are composed of directed acyclic graphs with only one parent and several children with a strong assumption of independence among child nodes in the context of their parent. The major advantage of the naive Bayes classifier is its short computational time for training [5]. Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are relatively new supervised machine learning technique. The key features of SVMs are the use of kernels, the absence of local minima, the sparseness of the solution and the capacity control obtained by optimizing the margin. Different types of SVM and SVM extensions have been proposed such as: Least squares support vector machine (LSSVM), Lagrangian support vector machine (LSVM), Newton support vector machine (NSVM), Smooth support vector machine (SSVM), Fuzzy support vector machine (FSVM) and Hidden space support vector machines (HSSVM) [6]. Ensemble learning techniques have been shown to increase machine learning accuracy by combining two or more classifiers, which are trained as separately and then combined to form a network of learners that has a higher accuracy than any single component [7].

II. THE PROPOSED CLASSIFIER

Let the training data $D_{train} = \{Y_{train}, X_{train}\}$ where $Y_{train} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$, $X_{train} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, the target y_i is the known label associated with the feature vector x_i , if there are m classes in the classification problem then $y_i \in A \subset \mathcal{R}$, $x_i \in B \subset \mathcal{R}^t$ and t is the number of the features. The proposed classifier consist from four components: Signal-to-Noise as a feature selection technique, support vector machine, Bayesian neural network and AdaBoost as an ensemble algorithm. Fig. 1 shows the components of the suggested classifier.

Fig. 1 The components of the suggested classifier.

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Signal-to-Noise ranks the features with the ratio of the "signal" (the difference between the mean values of the two classes), and the "noise" (the within class standard deviation). This criterion is similar to the Fisher criterion, the Ttest criterion, and the Pearson correlation coefficient. It can be thought of as a linear univariate feature ranking method. The top ranking features are selected and the new data matrix returned.

$$S2N = \frac{|\mu_+ - \mu_-|}{\sigma_+ + \sigma_-} \quad (1)$$

III. BAYESIAN NEURAL NETWORK

The Bayesian neural networks (BNN) is an algorithm of the neural networks trained by Bayesian statistics. It is not only suitable for the non-linear functions, but it also can be used to discover more general relationships in data than the traditional statistical methods. Furthermore, by using BNN we can avoid neural networks problems such as local maxima and overfitting.

The multilayer perceptron network, with a hidden layer and tanh activation function can be described as follows:

$$P(y_{new} | x_{new}, w) = f(x_{new}, w) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-g(x_{new}, w))}$$

Where

$$g(x_{new}, w) = b + \sum_{j=1}^H v_j \tanh(a_j + \sum_{i=1}^n u_{ji} x_i) \quad (3)$$

Where n is the dimensionality of the feature vectors, that is, the inputs, and H is the number of hidden nodes. The parameters $w = (b; v; a; u)$ are generally referred to as weights. The standard NN Learning can be viewed as maximum likelihood estimation for the network parameters. The value of weights \bar{w} is computed by maximizing:

$$\bar{w} = \prod_{i=1}^n p(y_i | x_i, w) \quad (4)$$

Where (y_i, x_i) are training case i . Thus the following conditional distribution can be used to classify the test data x_{new} :

$$P(y_{new} | x_{new}, \bar{w}) \quad W^T \cdot X - b = 0 \quad (8)$$

Unfortunately, using a single network, that is, a single point w_0 in the parameter space, difficulties with local maxima and overfitting can arise. In the Bayesian approach, one performs a weighted average over all points, that is, all networks. Bayesian predictions are found by integration rather than maximization. For a test case x_{new} , y_{new} is predicted using

$$P(y_{new} | x_{new}, X_{train}, Y_{train}) = \int P(y_{new} | x_{new}, w) P(w | X_{train}, Y_{train}) dw = \int f(x_{new}, w) (P(w | X_{train}, Y_{train})) dw \quad (5)$$

The above posterior distribution is

$$P(w | X_{train}, Y_{train}) = P(w) \frac{P(Y_{train} | X_{train}, w)}{\int P(w) P(Y_{train}, X_{train}, w) dw} \propto P(w) \prod_{i=1}^n P(y_i | x_i, w) \quad (6)$$

Every Bayesian inference requires the specification of a prior $P(w)$. Experience suggests that a reasonable class to choose from is the class of Gaussian priors centered at zero, which favors smaller rather than larger weights. Smaller weights yield smoother fits to data. For realistic applications, the dimensionality of the parameter space of the functions $f(x, w)$ is typically very complex. The integrations required by Bayesian approach can be approximated using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods, such as that implemented in the FBM software [8] and MCMCstuff Toolbox [9]. MCMC method is used to generate a sample of points, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k which are drawn from the posterior density $P(w | X_{train}, Y_{train})$. Thus the integral, can be approximated as following

$$P(y_{new} | x_{new}, X_{train}, Y_{train}) \approx \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k f(x_{new}, w_i) \quad (7)$$

IV. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINES

Support Vector Machines (SVM) have been successfully applied to a wide range of pattern recognition and classification problems including handwriting recognition, face detection, and microarray gene expression analysis. SVMs start from the goal of finding the maximum margin hyperplane which divides the target classes into two sets. Let the first target class equal to "1" and the second target class equal to "-1", the general hyperplane can be written as:

Where W is the weights and X is a vector. The hyperplane should separate the data, so that

$$W^T x_i + b \geq 1 \quad \text{for all the } x_i \text{ of one class, and} \\ W^T x_i + b \leq -1 \quad \text{for all the } x_i \text{ of the other class}$$

Let the target classes be $y_i \in \{1, -1\}$, then the above inequalities can be rewritten as

$$y_i (W^T x_i + b) \geq 1 \quad (9)$$

In the case of no hyperplane that can split the target classes, the Soft Margin method will choose a hyperplane that splits the classes with minimum error, and maximum margin, therefore, the SVM optimization problem can be rewritten as following:

$$\min_{W,b,\xi} \frac{1}{2} W^T W + C \sum_{i=1}^l \xi_i \quad (10)$$

Subject to

$$y_i (W^T x_i + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i$$

$$\xi_i \geq 0$$

For non-linear cases, the data must be mapped into a richer feature space. SVMs use an implicit mapping Φ of the input data into a high-dimensional feature space defined by a kernel function, then construct a hyperplane in that space. This allows us to apply the previous linear classification techniques to the non-linear features. A general kernel equation is:

$$k(x_1, x_2) = (t + x_1 \cdot x_2)^d e^{(-h \|x_1 - x_2\|^2)} \quad (11)$$

Mostly used kernels are:

Linear Kernel: $d=1, t=0$ and $h=0$.

Polynomial degree N Kernel: $d=N, t= \beta$ and $h=0$.

RBF Kernel: $d=0, t=0$ and $h= \gamma$.

Thus the Non-linear form is:

$$\min_{W,b,\xi} \frac{1}{2} W^T W + C \sum_{i=1}^l \xi_i \quad (12)$$

Subject to

$$y_i (W^T \Phi(x_i) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i$$

$$\xi_i \geq 0$$

There are two parameters while using RBF kernels: C and γ . It is not known which C and γ are the best for one problem; Consequently, parameter search must be performed before training the classifier [10].

V. ENSEMBLE LEARNING

Ensemble techniques for classification use a combination of many classifiers instead of using just one classifier[11]. One can try to obtain this result by taking a base learning algorithm and re-implementing it several times on different training sets.

Two popular Ensemble techniques exist: Bagging and AdaBoost. In Bagging each classifier is trained on a bootstrap replicate of the original training set. AdaBoost (short for Adaptive Boosting) was the particular variant of boosting. It adaptively changes distribution of training data by focusing more on previously misclassified records. Patterns that are wrongly classified will have their weights increased. Unlike Bagging, weights may change at the end of a boosting round. Algorithm 1 describes AdaBoost steps for k classifier.

Algorithm 1: AdaBoost

Input: n the size of the training set and the classifiers f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k , where is k the number of the classifiers.

Output: The final classifier $g(X)$.

Steps:

1- Let $\lambda_i^1 = 1, \forall i = 1 \dots n$

2- For $j = 1$ to k

$$2.1- \beta_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } f_j(x_i) \neq y_i \\ 0 & \text{if } f_j(x_i) = y_i \end{cases}$$

2.2- Use the classifier j to minimize the objective function:

$$\varepsilon_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^j \beta_j}{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^j}$$

$$2.3- w_j = \ln \frac{1 - \varepsilon_j}{\varepsilon_j}$$

2.4- for $i=1$ to n

$$\lambda_i^{j+1} = \lambda_i^j e^{w_j \beta_j}$$

3- The final classifier is

$$g(X) = \text{sign} \left(\sum_{j=1}^k w_j f_j(X) \right)$$

VI. DATASETS

Four classification problems are used. All the datasets have many features and one discrete target. The basic information about the datasets is summarized in Table 1. The following is a brief description about the datasets:

Breast Cancer: Features are computed from a digitized image of a fine needle aspirate (FNA) of a breast mass. They describe characteristics of the cell nuclei present in the image. Separating plane described above was obtained using Multisurface Method-Tree (MSM-T). a classification method

which uses linear programming to construct a decision tree. Relevant features were selected using an exhaustive search in the space of 1-4 features and 1-3 separating planes.

ARCENE: The task of ARCENE is to distinguish cancer *versus* normal patterns from mass spectrometric data. This is a two-class classification problem with continuous input variables. The data were obtained from two sources: The National Cancer Institute (NCI) and the Eastern Virginia Medical School (EVMS). All the data consist of mass-spectra obtained with the SELDI technique. The samples include patients with cancer (ovarian or prostate cancer), and healthy or control patients.

Statlog (Heart): is used to diagnose the heart disease. The attributes in this dataset include: the age, sex, chest pain type, resting blood pressure, serum cholesterol in mg/dl, fasting blood sugar, maximum heart rate achieved and the slope of the peak exercise ST segment.

MADOLON : The task of MADOLON is to classify random data. This is a two-class classification problem with sparse binary input variables. The data is synthetic. It was generated by a Matlab code.

TABLE I
 THE BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE DATASETS

Dataset	#Patterns	#Features	#Classes
Breast Cancer (BC)	569	10	2
ARCENE	200	10000	2
Statlog Heart (SH)	270	13	2
MADOLON	2600	500	2

Breast Cancer (BC) and Statlog Heart (SH) datasets Can be downloaded from the center of Machine Learning and Intelligent Systems at university of California <http://cml.ics.uci.edu/>. ARCENE and MADOLON datasets can be found at NIPS 2003 feature selection challenge site: <http://nipsfsc.ecs.soton.ac.uk/>.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Matlab 7.0, MCMCstuff toolbox and CLOP package are used to implement and to compare the state-of-art classification methods [9],[12]. A k-folding scheme with k=4 is applied to Breast Cancer (BC) and Statlog Heart (SH) datasets. The training procedure for each dataset is repeated 4 times, each time with 75% of the patterns as training and 25% for testing. All the reported results are obtained by averaging the outcomes of the 4 separate tests. In ARCENE dataset, 100 patterns are used for training and 100 patterns are used for testing. Whereas in MADOLON datasets, 2000 patterns are used for training and 600 patterns are used for testing. Several combinations of the preprocessing, feature selection and

classification methods are implemented. The preprocessing methods are:

- **ST:** Standardization of the columns of the data matrix (feature) by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation.
- **NM:** Normalization of the lines of the data matrix by dividing by the Euclidean norm.
- **SS:** Global data matrix normalization by subtracting shift and dividing by scale.
- **PCA:** Reducing the features using the principal component analysis.
- **SUB:** Selection of a subset of the training patterns.

The Feature selection methods:

- **GS:** Selection with Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization.
- **RE:** Ranking with the Relief score.
- **RF:** Ranking with Random Forests.
- **S2N:** Ranking with the signal-to-noise ratio.
- **RFE:** Ranking with recursive feature elimination using a SVC classifier.

The Classification methods:

- **KR:** Kernel Ridge Regression.
- **NA:** Naive Bayes.
- **NN:** Neural Network with one hidden layer.
- **RFC:** Random Forest Classifier.
- **NSVC:** Non-linear Support Vector Classifier.
- **LSVC:** Linear Support Vector Classifier.
- **BNN:** Bayesian Neural Network.
- **Proposed:** Ensemble of SVC and BNN.

Table 2 summarizes the balanced error rates (BER) and the area under the curve (AUC) for each method and each dataset. It is clear that the proposed method is the most accurate classifier and it has the lowest BER and the highest AUC. Accurate results can also be obtained by using nonlinear SVC and neural network with suitable pre-processing and feature selection methods such as methods 5, 9, 12 and 25.

Fig. 2 shows the BER of the top 15 accurate methods. It compares the contribution for each BER to a total across the methods. For example when the proposed method (method 26) is applied, the BER is 2.15 for BC and zero for the other datasets. whereas if method 22 is applied, then BER is 10.9, 15, 28.33 and 36.33 for BC, SH, ARCENE and MADOLON, respectively.

Table 3 shows the training and the testing time for each method. To find the time per pattern, we have to divide the shown time by the number of the patterns in the given dataset. The required training and testing time by the proposed method is acceptable with compare to other accurate methods such as method 5, 9, 12 and 25. It can be observed that the testing time needs less than 1/10 second per pattern for any dataset.

TABLE II
 THE BALANCED ERROR RATES (BER) AND THE AREA UNDER THE CURVE (AUC) FOR EACH METHOD

Method	Pre Process	Feature Selection	Classifier	CANCER		HEART		ARCENE		MADELON	
				BER	AUC	BER	AUC	BER	AUC	BER	AUC
1		GS	KR	8.53	96.7	10.83	95	9.9	96.96	38.5	66.92
2	PCA		KR	8.53	97.2	10.83	95	0.89	100	38.83	65.98
3	ST		LSVC	7.54	95.2	6.67	94.44	17.29	95.17	31.33	76.86
4	NM+SS	S2N	NA	50	87	49.17	75.56	50	78.21	39	68.06
5	ST		NSVC	6.15	97.8	10.83	96.11	0	100	0	100
6	RFE		SVC	7.54	96.3	6.67	94.44	0	100	38.33	65.01
7	ST	RE	NN	6.15	98.8	0	100	4.06	99.15	50	47
8		S2N+RF	RFC	20.2	93	20	92.78	0	100	0.5	99.99
9	ST+NM	S2N	NSVC	4.76	99.3	0	100	0	100	0.33	100
10			KR	8.53	97.2	10.83	95	0	100	26.83	80.43
11			NA	44.4	96.2	23.3	94.44	31.66	83.08	50	69.38
12			NN	5.15	98.5	0	100	39.94	60.43	50	51.19
13	NM		NA	47.2	96.2	20	95.56	31.66	82.75	50	68.6
14			NSVC	9.92	97.9	10.83	95.56	0	100	0	100
15	NM	RE	NSVC	9.52	98.8	3.33	98.89	0	100	0.5	99.96
16	PCA		NA	15.6	96.2	11.67	95	51.95	45.25	27.5	80.4
17		RE	NA	44.4	96.2	23.33	94.44	31.66	83.08	50	69.38
18		RF	NA	22.6	92.5	24.17	89.44	0	100	0	100
19			RFC	44.4	96.2	23.33	94.44	31.66	83.08	50	69.38
20		S2N	NA	44.4	96.2	23.33	94.44	31.66	83.08	50	69.38
21	SS		NA	47.6	96.2	33.33	94.44	31.66	83.08	50	69.38
22	ST		NA	10.9	96.2	15	94.44	28.33	83.08	36.33	69.38
23			LSVC	33.3	93.7	24.17	93.89	30.11	77.39	38	62.98
24		RFE	NA	44.4	96.2	23.33	94.44	31.66	83.08	50	69.38
25		S2N	BNN	6.15	98	0	100	0	100	0.5	99.96
26	NM	S2N	Proposed	2.15	99.6	0	100	0	100	0	100

Fig. 2 BER of the top 15 accurate methods

TABLE III
THE TRAINING AND THE TESTING TIME FOR EACH METHOD

Method	Pre Process	Feature Selection	Classifier	CANCER		HEART		ARCENE		MADELON	
				Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
1		GS	KR	0.04	0.01	0.047	0.015	3.616	0.81	2.4	0.234
2	PCA		KR	0.04	0.01	0.062	0.016	2.79	1.605	4.146	0.468
3	ST		LSVC	0.10	0.01	0.093	0.016	3.366	0.81	23.28	0.234
4	NM+SS	S2N	NA	0.07	0.03	0.062	0.015	0.686	0.811	0.717	0.374
5	ST		NSVC	0.12	0.04	0.125	0.032	5.222	13.06	53.25	89.96
6	RFE		SVC	0.20	0.01	0.14	0.016	8.806	0.794	58.86	0.233
7	ST	RE	NN	0.71	0.01	0.468	0.015	2.26	0.81	6.203	0.234
8		S2N+RF	RFC	0.01	0	0.032	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.109	0.093
9	ST+NM	S2N	NSVC	0.06	0.03	0.062	0.031	0.935	1.48	2.853	4.832
10			KR	0.01	0.01	0.016	0.016	0.421	0.218	4.099	0.047
11			NA	0.01	0	0.015	0	0.452	0.234	0.312	0.046
12			NN	0.49	0.01	0.343	0.016	16.24	0.311	6.375	0.078
13	NM		NA	0.01	0.01	0.016	0.016	0.702	0.624	0.53	0.172
14			NSVC	0.06	0.01	0.031	0.031	4.255	5.814	58.79	97.53
15	NM	RE	NSVC	0.14	0.03	0.063	0.031	1.917	0.841	6.188	2.743
16	PCA		NA	0.01	0.01	0.016	0.015	2.634	1.73	3.865	1.044
17		RE	NA	0.09	0.01	0.031	0.015	2.135	0.499	4.036	0.14
18		RF	NA	0.01	0.01	0.016	0.015	0.031	0.016	0.141	0.11
19			RFC	0.03	0.01	0.031	0.016	0.639	0.499	0.561	0.14
20		S2N	NA	0.01	0.01	0.015	0.016	0.872	0.514	0.608	0.124
21	SS		NA	0.01	0.01	0.015	0.015	0.733	0.608	0.515	0.172
22	ST		NA	0.01	0	0.016	0.015	0.982	0.81	0.639	0.234
23			LSVC	0.28	0.01	0.031	0.015	4.535	0.233	23.31	0.046
24		RFE	NA	298.	0	251.7	0.015	13.07	0.483	58.26	0.125
25		S2N	BNN	0.52	0.01	0.44	0.01	18.11	0.110	8.51	0.080
26	NM	S2N	Proposed	0.58	0.04	0.51	0.04	18.21	0.310	16.51	10.08

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